

Sequential Bayesian Phylogenetic Inference

Supporting Information

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1 S1 Toy example

2 In this section we provide the details for the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) analyses on the
3 toy example (see Figure 1 in the main text).

4 S1.1 Joint inference

5 The parameters and prior distribution for the joint inference of toy example corresponding to
6 Figure 1a are given in Table S1. A corresponding RevBayes script outlining all necessary details for
7 replicating this analysis are given in Listing 1. We ran the MCMC analyses for 1,000,000 iterations,
8 after a pre-burnin phase of 100,000 iterations, which is well beyond the normal chain length but the
9 obtain very smooth posterior distributions. The specific moves on the parameters can be retrieved
10 from the listing.

Table S1: Model parameter names and prior distributions for the toy example joint inference.

Parameter	X	$f(X)$
Prior mean	μ	Uniform(-10,10)
Prior standard deviation	σ	Uniform(0,10 ⁴)
Focal parameter	λ_i	Lognormal(μ, σ)
Observations	$x_{i,j}$	Poisson(λ_i)

```
1 mu ~ dnUniform(-10,10)
2 sigma ~ dnUniform(0,1E4)
3
4 idx <- 1
5 for (i in 1:10) {
6   lambdas[i] ~ dnLognormal(mu, sigma)
7   for (j in 1:M) {
8     x[idx] ~ dnPoisson(lambdas[i])
9     x[idx].clamp(data[idx])
10    idx++
11  }
12 }
13
14 moves.append( mvSlide(mu, delta=0.01) )
15 moves.append( mvScale(sigma, lambda=0.01) )
16
17 for (i in 1:NUMLAMBDAS) {
18   moves.append( mvScale(lambdas[i], lambda=0.01) )
19 }
20
21 monitors.append( mnModel(filename="output/joint_rep.log", printgen=10) )
22 monitors.append( mnScreen(mu, sigma, printgen=1000) )
23
24 mymcmc = mcmc(mymodel, monitors, moves)
```

```

25 mymcmc.burnin(1E5,100)
26 mymcmc.run(1E6)

```

Listing 1: Excerpt from the RevBayes script for the joint inference on the toy example.

11 S1.2 Stepwise Bayesian inference

12 In this next subsection, we provide more details about the stepwise Bayesian inference for the toy
13 example.

14 S1.2.1 Step 1

15 *Step 1* of the stepwise Bayesian inference estimates the importance distribution of the focal param-
16 eter. Thus, the hierarchical layer of the model is broken up and only the data layers are included
17 (see Table S2 and Figure 1b). Overall, *step 1* is very similar to the joint inference with the exception
18 that the hierarchical prior distribution is replaced by a uniform prior distribution. The remaining
19 MCMC settings stayed the same. Listing 2 shows the RevBayes script to perform *step 1* of the
20 stepwise Bayesian inference.

Table S2: Model parameter names and prior distributions for *step 1* of the stepwise Bayesian inference for the toy example.

Parameter	X	$f(X)$
Focal parameter	λ_i	Uniform(0, 10 ⁴)
Observations	$x_{i,j}$	Poisson(λ_i)

```

1 for (i in 1:10) {
2   lambdas[i] ~ dnUniform(0,1E4)
3   for (j in 1:M) {
4     x[idx] ~ dnPoisson(lambdas[i])
5     x[idx].clamp(data[idx])
6     idx++
7   }
8 }
9
10 for (i in 1:10) {
11   moves.append( mvScale(lambdas[i], lambda=0.01) )
12 }
13
14 monitors.append( mnFile(lambdas, filename="output/step1.log", printgen=10) )
15 monitors.append( mnScreen(printgen=1000) )
16
17 mymcmc = mcmc(mymodel, monitors, moves)
18 mymcmc.burnin(1E5,100)
19 mymcmc.run(1E6)

```

Listing 2: Excerpt from the RevBayes script for *Step 1* of the stepwise Bayesian inference on the toy example.

21 **S1.2.2 Step 2**

Table S3: Model parameter names and prior distributions for *step 2* of the stepwise Bayesian inference for the toy example.

Parameter	X	$f(X)$
Prior mean	μ	Uniform(-10, 10)
Prior standard deviation	σ	Uniform(0, 10^4)
Focal parameter	λ_i	Lognormal(μ, σ)

22 *Step 2* of the Bayesian stepwise inference takes the samples from the importance distribution
 23 generated in *step 1* as data. We achieve this using the function `readTrace`. How many samples
 24 are actually taken is controlled by the thinning argument, that is, when we performed our tests
 25 using a different number of samples N from *step 1* we simply applied a different thinning of the
 26 samples. The parameters and distributions for *step 2* are shown in Table S3 (see also Figure 1c).
 27 Compared to the joint inference, we do not have the layer including the data. Note that we use
 28 `dnEmpiricalSample` to represent the probability distribution for the importance sample. This
 29 `dnEmpiricalSample` is completely generic and can be used for any probability distribution.

```

1 samples = readTrace( file="output/step1.log", burnin=0.001, thin=1000)
2
3 mu ~ dnUniform(-10,10)
4 sigma ~ dnUniform(0,1E4)
5
6 for (i in 1:10) {
7   lambda_prior[i] = dnLognormal(mu, sigma)
8   lambdas[i] ~ dnEmpiricalSample(lambda_prior[i])
9   lambdas[i].clamp( samples[4+i].getValues() )
10 }
11
12 moves.append( mvScale(sigma, lambda=0.01) )
13 moves.append( mvSlide(mu, delta=0.01) )
14
15 monitors.append( mnFile(mu, sigma, filename="output/step2.log", printgen=10) )
16 mymcmc.burnin(1E5,100)
17 mymcmc.run(1E6)

```

Listing 3: Excerpt from the RevBayes script for *Step 2* of the stepwise Bayesian inference on the toy example.

30 S2 Relaxed Clock Analyses

31 In this section we describe the details of the relaxed clock analyses of the main text. The RevBayes
32 code snippets describe the main features of the analyses and only need to be adapted for the specific
33 data (*e.g.*, simulation replicate).

34 S2.1 Joint inference

35 First, we present the model for the joint Bayesian inference using the uncorrelated lognormal relaxed
36 clock model. All parameters are presented in Table S4. We used a Jukes-Cantor substitution model
37 [1] for simplicity and to speed up the simulation study. We used a uniform prior on node ages
38 conditional on the root age. We used a lognormal prior distribution on branch-specific clock rates
39 (uncorrelated lognormal relaxed clock [2]) with mean m_c (in real space, *i.e.*, not log-transformed)
40 and standard deviation sd_c . Both hyperparameter had a uniform prior distribution between 0 and
41 10,000.

Table S4: Model parameter names and prior distributions for the Bayesian relaxed clock example joint inference, see main text Figure 3.

Parameter	X	$f(X)$
Substitution rate matrix	Q	fixed to Jukes-Cantor model [1]
Mean clock rate	m_c	Uniform(0, 10 ⁴)
Standard deviation of clock rates	sd_c	Uniform(0, 10 ⁴)
Phylogeny	Ψ	UniformTimeTree(<i>root</i>)

42 The corresponding RevBayes code snippet is given in Listing 4. Note that we use our newly
43 developed distribution `dnBranchRateTree` here as the prior distribution on the phylogeny with
44 branch lengths in units of substitutions. In principle, the `root_branch_fraction` should not be a
45 parameter but an observation and thus should not have a prior distribution. Here we used a uniform
46 prior distribution that does not affect the outcome because all values are equally probable. Ideally,
47 our implementation would integrate analytically or numerically over the `root_branch_fraction`.
48 This might be implemented in a future version.

49 The MCMC simulation was run again for 1,000,000 iterations after a pre-burnin phase of 100,000
50 iterations. Note that multiple moves were applied per iteration where the average number of moves
51 corresponds to the specified weights. That is, for 8 taxa we used 31 moves per iterations.

```
1 Q <- fnJC(4)
2
3 clock_rate_mean ~ dnUniform(0,1E4)
4 clock_rate_sd ~ dnUniform(0,1E4)
5
6 clock_rate_ln_mean := ln(clock_rate_mean)
7 branch_rate_prior = dnLognormal(clock_rate_ln_mean , clock_rate_sd)
8
9 time_tree ~ dnUniformTimeTree(rootAge=ROOT_AGE, taxa=taxa)
10 time_tree.setValue( true_tree )
11
```

```

12 root_branch_fraction ~ dnBeta(1,1)
13
14 psi ~ dnBranchRateTree( time_tree , branch_rate_prior , root_branch_fraction )
15
16 seq ~ dnPhyloCTMC( tree=psi , Q=Q, type="DNA" )
17 seq.clamp( data )
18
19 moves.append( mvScale( clock_rate_mean , weight=3 ) )
20 moves.append( mvScale( clock_rate_sd , weight=3 ) )
21 moves.append( mvNodeTimeSlideUniform( time_tree , weight=NUMTAXA ) )
22 moves.append( mvBetaProbability( root_branch_fraction , weight=2.0 ) )
23 moves.append( mvBranchLengthScale( psi , weight=n.branches ) )
24
25 monitors.append( mnFile( time_tree , filename="output/joint.trees" , printgen=1 ) )
26 monitors.append( mnModel( filename="output/joint.log" , printgen=1 ) )
27
28 mymcmc.burnin( 1E5, 100 )
29 mymcmc.run( 1E6 )

```

Listing 4: Excerpt from the RevBayes script for the joint inference using the Bayesian relaxed clock example.

52 S2.2 Stepwise Bayesian inference

53 In this next subsection, we provide more details about the stepwise Bayesian inference for the
54 Bayesian relaxed clock example.

55 S2.2.1 Step 1

56 *Step 1* of the stepwise Bayesian inference estimates the importance distribution of the phylogeny
57 with branch lengths in units of substitutions. Thus, the hierarchical layer of the model is broken up
58 and only the data layers are included (see Table S2 and Figure 3b). Overall, *step 1* is very similar
59 to the joint inference with the exception that the uniform node age prior distribution on the time
60 tree together with the branch rate prior distribution is replaced by a prior distribution directly
61 on unrooted trees (`dnUniformTopologyBranchLength`). The remaining MCMC settings stayed the
62 same. Listing 5 shows the RevBayes script to perform *step 1* of the stepwise Bayesian inference.

Table S5: Model parameter names and prior distributions for *step 1* of the stepwise Bayesian inference for the Bayesian relaxed clock example.

Parameter	X	$f(X)$
Substitution rate matrix	Q	fixed to Jukes-Cantor model [1]
Phylogeny	Ψ	<code>UniformBranchLengthTree(blPrior = Uniform(0, 1000))</code>

```

1 Q <- fnJC( 4 )
2
3 psi ~ dnUniformTopologyBranchLength( taxa , dnUniform( 0, 1E3 ) )

```

```

4 psi.setValue( true_tree_unrooted )
5
6 moves.append( mvBranchLengthScale(psi, weight=n_branches) )
7
8 monitors.append( mnFile(psi, filename="output/step1.trees", printgen=10) )
9 monitors.append( mnScreen(printgen=1000) )
10
11 mymcmc = mcmc(mymodel, monitors, moves)
12 mymcmc.burnin(1E5,100)
13 mymcmc.run(1E6)

```

Listing 5: Excerpt from the RevBayes script for *Step 1* of the stepwise Bayesian inference on the Bayesian relaxed clock example.

63 S2.2.2 Step 2

64 *Step 2* of the Bayesian stepwise inference takes the samples from the importance distribution
65 generated in *step 1* as data. We achieve this using the function `readTreeTrace`. How many
66 samples are actually taken is controlled by the thinning argument, that is, when we performed our
67 tests using a different number of samples N from *step 1* we simply applied a different thinning of
68 the samples. The parameters and distributions for *step 2* are shown in Table S6 (see also Figure 3c).
69 Compared to the joint inference, we do not have the layer including the data. Note that we use
70 `dnEmpiricalSample` to represent the probability distribution for the importance sample. This
71 `dnEmpiricalSample` is completely generic and can be used for any probability distribution.

Table S6: Model parameter names and prior distributions for *step 2* of the stepwise Bayesian inference for the Bayesian relaxed clock example.

Parameter	X	$f(X)$
Mean clock rate	m_c	Uniform(0, 10 ⁴)
Standard deviation of clock rates	m_{sd}	Uniform(0, 10 ⁴)
Phylogeny	Ψ	UniformTimeTree(<i>root</i>)

```

1 treetrace = readTreeTrace("output/step1.trees",
2                           treetype="non-clock",
3                           burnin=0.001,
4                           thin=1000)
5
6 clock_rate_mean ~ dnUniform(0,1E4)
7 clock_rate_sd ~ dnUniform(0,1E4)
8
9 clock_rate_ln_mean := ln(clock_rate_mean)
10
11 branch_rate_prior = dnLognormal(clock_rate_ln_mean, clock_rate_sd)
12
13 time_tree ~ dnUniformTimeTree(rootAge=ROOTAGE, taxa=taxa)
14 time_tree.setValue( true_tree )

```

```

15
16 root_branch_fraction ~ dnBeta(1,1)
17
18 phis ~ dnEmpiricalSample(
19     dnBranchRateTree( time_tree , branch_rate_prior , root_branch_fraction ) )
20 phis.clamp( treetrace.getTrees() )
21
22
23 moves.append( mvScale( clock_rate_mean , weight=3 ) )
24 moves.append( mvScale( clock_rate_sd , weight=3 ) )
25 moves.append( mvNodeTimeSlideUniform( time_tree , weight=NUMTAXA ) )
26 moves.append( mvBetaProbability( root_branch_fraction , weight=2.0 ) )
27
28 monitors.append( mnFile( time_tree , filename="output/step2.trees" , printgen=10 ) )
29
30 mymcmc.burnin(1E5,100)
31 mymcmc.run(1E6)

```

Listing 6: Excerpt from the RevBayes script for *Step 2* of the stepwise Bayesian inference on the Bayesian relaxed clock example.

72 S2.3 Results

73 For completeness, we present here the results from the toy example showing (a) more observations,
74 and (b) posterior distributions for the mean parameter μ .

75 S3 Divergence time estimation in insects

Figure S1: Estimated posterior distributions for the simple toy example as shown in Figure 1. In each row, we show the posterior distributions for different numbers of observations (columns) and different number of samples used in *step 2* (colors). The top row shows the posterior distributions of σ and the middle row the posterior distribution of μ . The bottom row shows the posterior and importance distribution of an arbitrarily picked λ_i . We observe that with few samples the joint and stepwise inferences disagree (left column; top row) which is due to divergence of the posterior distribution and importance distribution (left column; bottom row). Joint and stepwise inference are identical for many observations (right column). More samples M of the importance distribution in *step 2* are beneficial but have a smaller impact than the number of observations.

Figure S2: Posterior distribution of the divergence time of four clades based on [3]: polyneoptera, diptera, parasitic lice, dictyoptera and sister clade. The plots show the difference in the posterior distribution depending on the node calibration strategy; either mixed between hard-uniform and lognormal (red), only soft-bounded uniform distributions (blue), or soft-uniform with the additional node calibration (green). The different rows show the difference in posterior distribution of the age when using different data sources; either posterior samples of trees from the DNA supermatrix (top), the protein supermatrix with empirical substitution models (AA; middle), or the protein supermatrix with the CAT-GTR substitution model (PhyloBayes; bottom).

Figure S3: Posterior distribution of clock rate standard deviation parameter of the lognormal distribution (uncorrelated lognormal relaxed clock). The plots show the difference in the posterior distribution depending on the node calibration strategy; either mixed between hard-uniform and lognormal (red), only soft-bounded uniform distributions (blue), or soft-uniform with the additional node calibration (green). The different columns show the difference in posterior distribution of the age when using different data sources; either posterior samples of trees from the DNA supermatrix (left), the protein supermatrix with empirical substitution models (AA; middle), or the protein supermatrix with the CAT-GTR substitution model (PhyloBayes; right).

76 **References**

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